

RESULTS OF PATHOLOGOANATOMIC EXAMINATION OF RABBITS
EUMIERIOSIS

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Аннотация. В статье изложены подробные сведения по полученным результатам и методам патологоанатомического вскрытия кроликов, спонтанно инфицированных и павших от инвазионного заболевания эймериоз в результате отсутствия лечебных мероприятий в хозяйствах.

Ключевые слова: кролики, патологоанатомическое вскрытие, эймериоз, катарально-геморрагический энтерит, геморрагический тифлит, токсическая дистрофия, атрофия мышц.

Abstract. The article presents detailed information on the results obtained and methods of pathological anatomical autopsy of rabbits spontaneously infected and dying from the invasive disease eimeriosis due to the lack of treatment measures on farms.

Key words: rabbits, postmortem examination, eimeriosis, catarrhal-hemorrhagic enteritis, hemorrhagic typhlitis, toxic dystrophy, muscle atrophy.

Introduction: It is important to improve the efficiency of the rabbit breeding network in livestock farming of the present era, when ensuring food safety is considered an urgent task. In the fulfillment of this urgent task, the development of animal husbandry plays an important role, it is observed that the
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increase in the number of rabbits in the small sector is prevented by some diseases that occur in them, and the introduction of effective methods of prevention and treatment of pathological processes is a necessity in the production of this sector. Because in recent years, rabbit diseases (Eymeriosis, etc.) have not been studied by researchers in our country.

Some infectious and parasitic diseases hinder the development and productivity of rabbit farming, which is a small branch of animal husbandry. In particular, colibacteriosis among infectious diseases, and eimeriosis among parasitic diseases have a special place among them. In the process of industrial development of large rabbit farms, colibacteriosis and eimeria spread widely among rabbits and cause great economic damage to farms.

Relevance of the topic. Eimeria is an invasive disease caused by single-celled simple parasites - Eimeria. Eimeria in rabbits has different clinical forms. Rabbits up to 3 months of age are severely affected by eimeria. When the disease is accompanied by complex pathological changes, rabbits lose their appetite due to disturbances in the digestive system, their mobility decreases sharply, their nutrition slows down, intestinal activity is disturbed (diarrhoea), diarrhea is sometimes mixed with blood, as a result, rabbits stop growing and die. cases are observed. The use of highly effective means for timely diagnosis, differentiation, treatment and prevention of the disease provides an opportunity for early recovery of sick rabbits and helps to reduce economic damage. As a result of eimeria, rabbits lag behind in growth and development, lose 12-30% of their weight, and if treatment and preventive measures are not carried out, the death rate of young rabbits reaches 85-100%.

Level of study of the problem. The causative agent of rabbit eimeria belongs systematically to Protozoa animal world, Apicomplexa type, Sporozoa

class, Coccidiida family, eimeriidae family, eimerinae subfamily and eimeria genus. One of these eimeria species is eimeria stiedae in rabbit liver, other species are e.perforans, e.media, e. magna, and e.irresidua parasitizes the intestine and causes pathological processes.

Like all spores, rabbit eimeria undergoes three stages of development: 1st stage - reproduction by schizogony or multiple asexual divisions; 2 - period - gametogony or sexual reproduction; The 3rd stage - reproduces by sporogony or asexual reproduction by forming sporozoites (with the presence of a host, the formation of spores that protect their developing from the impact of the external environment).

Three forms of rabbit eimeriosis are distinguished depending on the location of eimeria in the animal organ: 1. Intestinal, 2. Liver, 3. Mixed forms. In practice, the mixed form of invasion plays an important role. At the beginning of the disease, the intestines of the rabbit are damaged, then the liver is invaded, and as a result, the mixed form begins. After the latent period of infection, the rabbits become limp, lose their usual mobility, and lie on their stomachs. His appetite decreases and he stops eating. Abdominal cavity swells and gives pain, stool becomes liquid, sometimes mixed with mucus and blood. Sick rabbits stop growing, lose weight, and their fur is wrinkled. Urinary excretion is accelerated. Sometimes the secretion of saliva increases, the mucous membrane of the nose becomes catarrhally inflamed and conjunctivitis develops. With the start of inflammatory processes in the liver, the body becomes sluggish, the rabbit becomes indifferent to the external environment and lies down for a long time. He loses his appetite, his stomach is swollen, and he feels pain when he presses on his right side. The visible mucous membranes turn yellow, the muscles of the legs and neck become paralyzed and begin to tremble, and then they die in 7-10 days.

Patho-anatomical examination - dead and suspected diseased rabbits were dissected with the help of experts. External appearance of the rabbit bodies: The rabbit body is very thin, the mucous membranes of the eyes and mouth are liquid in color, anemia, the fur around the rear exit hole is contaminated with bloody, slimy feces. Skeletal muscles are liquid in color, in a state of atrophy. The mucous membranes of the mouth, throat, and esophagus are blue in color. Internal appearance: There is a small amount of food in the stomach. The serous membranes of the small intestine were reddened with a focus, several 1-2 mm shiny necrosis foci were formed. The chyme in the intestine is semi-liquid, white-reddish in color. Mucous membranes are swollen, reddened, demarcated, fluid-colored coverings, between which blood is visible, when a smear is taken from the fluid foci and microscopically examined, it is found that there are many round and oval oocysts.

Characteristic changes: cases of expansion and swelling of the cecum, outer serous membranes are dark red in color, hard consistency when palpated, blood clots with a dark layer on the cut surface and eroded mucous tissue were detected.

Due to the growth of connective tissue in the biliary tract of the liver, papilloma-like growths and bumps with a solid consistency are visible. In the capsule and parenchyma of the liver, linear, line-shaped swellings of a liquid color were formed. When they were cut, a liquid semi-liquid mass flowed out, when the smears were examined under a microscope, it was found that there were many oocysts of Eimeria.

Pathologo-anatomical diagnosis: 1. Catarrhal-hemorrhagic enteritis; 2. Hemorrhagic typhoid; 3. Toxic dystrophy of the liver; 4. Atrophy of skeletal muscles;

The final diagnosis: Eimeria (a protozoan disease caused by Eimeria parasitism, the death of rabbits was caused by Eimeria).

According to the results of the research on rabbit eimeriosis, it was once again noted that the spread of invasion in two districts depends on the factors contributing to the development of the epizootic condition, the conditions of keeping rabbits, feeding and effective implementation of preventive measures. In particular, the spread of the disease is relatively low due to the effective use of the latest modern technologies by the private enterprise "Maqsudabonu Business Service" and the use of enriched supplements for feeding, while the extent of infestation is high in the farm "Boriboy Mustaev Zamin Nur". , insufficient hygienic facilities for storage and lack of quality soft feed for feeding, feeding rabbits with different foods are the main reasons for the spread of the disease.

As a result of the conducted research, it was found that the extent of infestation in the farm "Boriboy Mustaev Zamin Nur" is 40-42%, and in the private enterprise "Maqsudabonu biznes servis" it is 10-15%.

Characteristic changes were noted during the pathologo-anatomical examination of the bodies of infected and dead rabbits, and rabbit eimeriosis was definitely diagnosed.

According to the results of our inspections of various breeds of rabbits on the unhealthy "Boriboy Mustayev Zamin Nur" farm in Bulung'ur district, in the spring of the year, 4 heads of Hikol rabbits, 2 heads of California rabbits, Velikan 1 case of death occurred in purebred rabbits, no case of death was observed in domestic rabbits, in total 7 head rabbits if death occurred, 2 of them, i.e. 28.57%, died due to liver disease, 3, i.e. 42.85%, died due to intestinal disease, the rest it was found that two heads, i.e. 28.57%, died with a mixed form of eimeria.

According to our research in the summer, one head of Hikol and California rabbits died, Velikan and local rabbits did not die, one head of rabbits died in the

summer with intestinal form of eimeria, and another head with mixed form. it was revealed in our pathologo-anatomical examinations.

According to our pathologo-anatomical examination in autumn, 2 of the 4 dead rabbits belonged to the Hikol, 1 California, and 1 Velikan breeds, and no deaths were observed in domestic rabbits. It was found that one of these 4 rabbits died from the liver form of eimeria, two from the intestinal form of eimeria, and one from the mixed form of eimeria.

According to our pathologoanatomical examination in the winter, 6 of the Hikol rabbits on the farm died, 3 of the California rabbits, 2 of the Velikan rabbits and 1 of the local rabbits died due to Eimeria oocysts. was noted, according to the results of the pathologoanatomical examination, a total of 12 heads died It was found that 3 rabbits, i.e. 25.0%, died from the liver form of eimeria, 5 heads, i.e. 41.66%, from the intestinal form of eimeria, and the remaining 4 rabbits, i.e. 33.33%, died from the mixed form of eimeria.

"Bo'riboy Mustayev Zamin Nur" FX rabbits results of pathologoanatomical examination

№		A type of rabbit					Check result					
		khikol	California	giant	Local	total	Liver		intestine		mixed	
							the number	%	the number	%	the number	%
1	Spring	4	2	1	-	7	2	28,57%	3	42,86	2	28,57
2	summer	1	1	0	-	2	-	-	1	50,0%	1	50,0%
3	Autumn	2	1	1	-	4	1	25,0%	2	50,0%	1	25,0%
4	Winter	6	3	2	1	12	3	25,0%	5	41,66%	4	33,33%
5	total	13	7	4	1	25	6	24,0%	11	44,0%	8	32,0%

Summary. Of the 25 dead rabbits, 13 belonged to the Khikol breed, 7 to the Californian breed, 4 to the giant breed, and 1 to the local breed. The prevalence of the disease was 24.0% for the liver form of eimeria, 44% for the intestinal form of eimeria. 0% and 32.0% in mixed eimeria.

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